

Overview of Global Circular Economy

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Thanh Long Vu ⁽²⁾Quang Khanh Pham ⁽³⁾Thi Dung Nguyen
⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾⁽³⁾University of Economics - Technology for Industries, Vietnam

Correspondence: Thanh Long Vu, 456 Minh Khai, Hai Ba Trung, Ha Noi

Abstract:

The goal of this article is to review research and theoretical basis related to circular economy. As a new approach in the way resources are treated, the circular economy is gaining attention worldwide for being the solution for the conflict between economic development and environmental protection. Research has shown that the transition towards a circular economy at both domestic and global level has close linkage to international trade, i.e. the trade in second-hand goods, end-of-life products, secondary materials, and waste

Keywords: Circular economy, international trade

1. Introduction

With a growing population of more than 7 billion people living on earth, our need for resources also increases consequently. According to estimation by GFN (2018), we now need 1.7 earths to meet the world's resource needs today.¹⁰ The UN estimates that since 1970, the world's total amount of raw materials used has tripled and could double by 2050 without intervention. This is beyond the supply of the Earth's natural resources. Resource supply and resource efficiency apparently become the challenge that we need to handle.

Statistics in World Bank 2018 report shows that global cities in 2016 generated about 2.01 billion tons of solid waste in urban areas with at least 33% of that being managed in an environmentally unsafe way. With population growth and urbanization, this figure could increase by 70% to 3.40 billion tons by 2050. By 2025, the value of the global waste management industry is expected to hit USD \$530 billion, from \$330.6 billion in 2017.

As natural resources become increasingly more expensive and difficult to source, the solution is to keep existing products and materials in circulation for as long as possible, extracting the maximum value from them. However, looking at the linear economy model (Figure 3) of extraction, transformation (production), utilization (consumption) and disposal that has been in operation for more than 150 years since the Industrial Evolution, it appears to only cause resource depletion and waste increase rather than to be a proper solution. This traditional model has shown its drawback of a great pressure on the environment in the context of climate change, environmental pollution due to the poor management of waste and the exhaustion of natural resources plus the high price of resources in general. Taking plastic waste as an example, by 2050, it is estimated that the volume of plastic waste discharged into the sea will be more than the total volume of fishes.

In order to minimize harm to the quality of life, it is necessary to have solutions to recycle waste, use recycled materials as input materials for production to save natural resources. The rational management and use of natural resources with the principle of "Closing the loop" through the efficient use of renewable raw materials and waste management by recycling to minimize value optimization has been embedded in the theory of circular economy, where products and materials are kept flowing in the economy for the longest. This circular economy can be achieved by designing products with their whole life cycle in mind, allowing them to be maintained in use for longer, then reused and refurbished to extend their lifetime, and, when their life is deemed over, recycled to create new products from old without the need for virgin raw materials.

2. Literature review

2.1. Circular economy

As reported in the Summary of the Second World Circular Economy Forum, held on 22 – 24 October, 2018²⁰, the work on circular economy builds on contemporary ideas developed by, namely, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation and others such as Walter Stahel (performance economy), William McDonough and Michael Braugart (cradle to-cradle design), Janine Benyus (biomimicry); and Amory and Hunter Lovins and Paul Hawken (natural capitalism), and Gunter Pauli (blue economy systems).

In 2018, Walker and his colleagues presented in their research that the notions of a circularity and non-linear thinking are not new, the principle of early circular economy strategies were initially designed to focus on waste management, embedded in “3Rs theory: Reuse – Reduce – Recycle” but gradually evolved to include more systematic approaches for the whole economy to include the 6Rs (reuse, recycle, re- design, remanufacture, reduce, recover). Under current circular economy systems adopted by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, products are designed to be restorative and regenerative, where products are utilized at their highest value.

In 2008, China became the pioneer in the transition towards circular economy with its adoption of the first circular economy promotion law in the world. China was then followed by other countries with a considerable number of both national and multinational initiatives (See further in Section II). For example, in 2016, Finland became the first country in the world to ever develop a national Roadmap towards a circular economy named “Leading the Cycle – Finish Road Map to a Circular Economy 2010 – 2025”, which was then included in the organization of the first World Circular Economy Forum 2017.

Definition of circular economy

Lately, Kirchherr, Reike and Kekkert (2017) have discovered 114 different definitions of circular economy. Their analysis’s findings indicate that circular economy is frequently conceptualized as the combination of reduce, reuse and recycle activities and the definitions show few explicit linkages of the circular economy concept to sustainable development²².

Circular economy emphasizes the management and regeneration of resources in a closed loop to avoid waste generation. Resource utilization comes in many ways, from redesigning, reducing, repair, reuse, recycling, material sharing or leasing. Circular economy could be simply understood as one in which products are recycled, repaired or reused rather than thrown away, and in which waste from one process becomes an input into other processes²³. Ellen MacArthur Foundation, in its 2012 report has defined circular economy as “an industrial system that is restorative and regenerative by intention and design. It places the “end-of-life” concept with restoration, shifts towards the use of renewable energy, eliminates the use of toxic chemicals, which repair, reuse, and aims for the elimination of waste through the superior design of materials, products, systems, and, within this, business models”.

Figure 1. The circular economy

Source: Ellen MacArthur Foundation, *Circular Economy systems diagram* (Feb, 2019),

Circular Economy now has received much attention globally and there is still no fixed definition for circular economy. The circular economy concept has been applied differently due to diverse cultural, social and political systems globally. 24 For instance, the CE has been implemented as the national development strategy in the U.K, or for waste management as in some European countries like Denmark, Switzerland, and Portugal, or aimed at reducing land use for waste disposal by focusing on solid waste avoidance and closed-loop recycling, solid waste management in Japan, or to achieve the goal of profitable product development, and improving industry management in China.

The research in 2018 of Walker et al. has found that current applications of the CE follow three thematic categories including eco-industrial network establishment; application to specific waste or recyclable resource streams, such as wood, paper, plastics and metals; and system-wide technical innovation to redefine products and services to design waste out, whilst minimizing negative environmental and economic impacts. However, these three CE themes are generally accepted within an individual developed country’s jurisdiction, yet is considered waste or pollution transfer once waste circulation or reutilization is exported to a developing country.

Benefits of circular economy

What we are facing now is the paradox caused by economic development and environmental protection. Now, we seem to have the answer for circular economy brings both economic and environmental benefits. Economically, the new economic model named “circular economy” presents “the opportunity to gradually

decouple economic growth from virgin resource inputs, encourage innovation, increase growth, and create more robust employment".²⁶ The potential benefits of shifting to a circular economy also extends into the natural environment by designing out waste and pollution, keeping products and materials in use, and regenerating, rather than degrading, natural systems, by which we achieve the global climate targets.

The 2016 report of the Ellen MacArthur Foundation and the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) estimated that India could generate economic value rising to US \$ 218 billion in 2030 and US \$ 624 billion in by 2050, by enforcing the principles of a circular economy in three areas: construction activities in cities; agriculture and food; vehicle fabrication and motion technology. The report also points out that the it could help the South Asian nation reduce its greenhouse gas emissions by 23% by 2030 and 44% by 2050, while significantly reducing material use. For China, the authors of the report point out that the application of the principles of circular economy in cities can create more affordable goods and services for urban residents, reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 23% and traffic congestion by 47% by 2040. Statistics show that during the period 1980-2010, China's economic size expanded 18 times, but energy consumption increased by only 5 times thanks to the application of new circular economy approach.

As Schoroeder has pointed out in 2018, circular economy can have a direct impact on more than 10 of the total 17 UN sustainable development goals; 134 of 169 specific targets are closely related to circular economy²⁷. Therefore, circular economy strategies could help lower-income countries 'leapfrog' to a more sustainable development pathway that avoids locking in resource-intensive economic practices of the dominant linear consumption and production system.

In its research paper 'An Inclusive Circular Economy. Priorities for Developing Countries' (May 2019), Chatham House notes that, under the right enabling conditions, the circular economy could provide new opportunities for economic diversification, value creation and skills development – going beyond waste management and recycling. With enough investment, developing countries could leapfrog developed countries in digital and materials innovation aimed at sustainable production and consumption patterns.

The so-far transition towards Circular Economy

Being potentially beneficial, the transition towards circular economy has become a global trend today. Political interest in the transition to a more resource efficient and circular economy is emerging in various corners of the world. At the international level, efforts towards a resource efficient economy began in the late 2000s and have achieved increased emphasis more recently in the framework of the G7 Alliance on Resource Efficiency, UN Sustainable Development Goals, and the European Union Circular Economy Action Plan. At the national level, policy action has taken place for instance in China, Finland, France, and the Netherlands in establishing circular economy roadmaps, Japan in implementing the Fundamental Law for Sound Material-Cycle Society, and the United States in launching the Sustainable Materials Management Action Plan (OECD, 2018).

A pioneer in promoting circular economy is Japan. The country enacted the Basic Act for Establishing a Sound Material-Cycle Society in 2001 and the Fundamental Plan for Establishing a Sound Material-Cycle Society in 2003, showing its leadership through the G8/G7 process and the Region 3R Forum in Asia and the Pacific. European Commission does not lag behind either. It adopted a Circular Economy Package in 2015 to stimulate Europe's transition towards a circular economy. The Package was then followed by a Circular Economy Finance Support Platform in 2016 and EU Strategy for Plastics. Joint actions are also seen with the handshake of the EU and China with the signing of a joint Memorandum of Understanding on Circular Economy Cooperation at the 20th EU-China Summit in 2018.

In 2018, the World Economic Forum, the World Resources Institute, Philips, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, the United Nations Environment Program and more than 40 partners launched the Circular Economy Promotion Forum to promote initiatives to expand this economic model. So far, there have been about 34 countries with 118 typical models of implementation of this shift, starting from the formulation of strategies, action plans, to

the promulgation of economic policies and laws in order to determine the responsibilities of manufacturers, citizens and the state, promote the development of environmental industries, create a market to provide waste treatment services to mobilize private resources and reduce investment.

In Vietnam, some circular economy models were implemented with certain effects, however, it has not been focused yet. Therefore, to promote the development of the circular economy in Vietnam, it is necessary to institutionalize and legalize the circular economy, aiming to implement the circular economy in all activities.

Regardless of the efforts put forward, our world is only 9% circular and the trend is negative. ³⁰The Circularity Gap is not closing. In the 12 months since the first Circularity Gap Report, the upward trend in resource extraction and greenhouse gas emissions has continued.

2.2. The impact of circular economy on trade flows

Many countries are taking action to adopt circular economy policies by closing material loops through the promotion of reuse, recycling and new business models, extending material loops through eco-design, and narrowing loops through resource efficiency initiatives. While these policies are largely considered at the domestic level, they exist in the context of a global economy and international value chains, therefore there is increasing awareness that a transition towards a more resource efficient and circular economy has broad linkages with international trade. This for instance takes place through the emergence of global value chains as well as trade in second-hand goods, end-of-life products, secondary materials or non-hazardous waste, as well as trade in related services.

Trade will be a powerful tool for fostering engagement from both the public and private sectors in regional and global circular value chains. Trade-focused circular economy discussions have the potential to open up new perspectives on opportunities for mutual gain, and to shape a global and inclusive vision that goes beyond the zero-sum world implied by some circular economy strategies today. This will be critical to expanding the markets for circular goods and services, pooling innovation knowledge bases, optimizing circular value chains, attracting cross-border investment and providing entrepreneurs with access to data while delivering an inclusive approach³².

International trade flows may shift according to structural changes induced by a circular economy (See Figure 7). Circular economy may lead to the decrease in import demand for primary and secondary materials and also decrease in exports of wastes and scrap.

For Goods

As argued by Felix P., Johanna L., and Laura W., (2019), domestic trade policies potentially provide an important means through which national governments can encourage and incentivize a transition to more circular approaches. The adoption of circular economy policies and measures will likely encourage trade in secondary goods, including materials and waste for recycling and energy recovery, secondary raw materials, second-hand goods, and goods for refurbishment and remanufacturing³⁴. Products that reach the end of their operational life can be exported to other countries as secondary goods for further consumption, as secondary materials for production feedstock, or as materials and waste for further processing.

Energy-efficiency requirements for imported second-hand vehicles; minimum percentage requirements for recyclable content in plastic waste; health and safety standards for recycled or recyclable products and materials; and quality, health and safety standards for remanufactured products³⁶ – all could, depending on how they are designed, either expand or restrict international trade in various categories of desirable and undesirable secondary materials.

Import duties can have a substantial impact on access to affordable inputs for circular economy activities in developing countries. The reduction or removal of import duties on primary goods used for pollution

management and resource management – such as equipment used in recycling plants – or on secondary raw materials can lower the capital costs of circular economy infrastructure and feedstock in import-dependent countries and boost the competitiveness of downstream circular economy activities.

For Services

Increased demand for services related to the sharing economy and provided by so-called ‘collaborative sectors’ could bring new opportunities for trade in services³⁷. Countries with a large, young and digitally workforce may look to export software services, for example, while countries with abundant manual labor may see new market opportunities in providing remanufacturing services for imported used goods. By the same token, architects overseeing the construction of new building stock in developing countries may, for example, elect to employ lighting services from overseas lighting companies rather than take ownership of the lighting equipment itself and assume responsibility for its maintenance and refurbishment³⁸. Trade opportunities and new trade flows could also emerge in various environmental services related to recycling, waste management and waste-to-energy generation.

For developing countries, the removal of restrictions on trade in services relevant to the circular economy across various modes of delivery (such as measures that restrict domestic businesses’ access to operating licenses overseas, or to foreign services in IT and communications) will be critical to promoting a more inclusive approach to the circular economy. Developed countries could benefit from repair services, for appliances and other goods, based in developing countries. Developing countries could benefit from the expertise of specialized companies in the sorting and processing of e-waste.

3. Circular economy initiatives in some countries

CE may offer opportunities for bilateral investments and partnerships which simultaneously contribute to the CE at home and overseas. The EU, China and Japan have been proactive in seeking out cross-border opportunities for partnership on the CE. The EU has dispatched CE missions to Japan, Indonesia and India (2018), Columbia (2017), Chile, China (2016). The focus of these missions is to communicate the opportunities from transitioning to a CE, as well as to support European businesses in expanding their activities in these countries. In June 2018, the EU and India signed a joint declaration of intent to foster resource-efficient practices in India and support recommendations made in the Strategy on Resource Efficiency. A number of joint initiatives will be undertaken, including support for an eco-labelling scheme for secondary products; assistance in developing recycling standards for e-waste, plastics, and construction and demolition waste; promotion of R&D in resource efficiency; and development of a ‘Waste Exchange Platform’, a marketplace for by-products and industrial waste.

In China, President Xi Jinping has stipulated that the Belt and Road Initiative

–centered on infrastructure building to connect China’s less developed border regions with Southeast Asia, Central Asia and Europe – should promote a ‘green, low-carbon, circular and sustainable’ form of development. One example is the planned construction of a China-African Circular Economy Industrial Park in South Africa.

Japan, meanwhile, has demonstrated regional leadership in the CE through its inauguration of the Regional 3R Forum in Asia and the Pacific. This cooperative platform enables governments from 39 countries in the region to promote the piloting of CE projects. As G20 chair in 2019, Japan has an opportunity to take its domestic and regional experience on to the international stage, building on the work started by Germany two years ago, and to promote policy alignment and knowledge exchange on resource efficiency and the CE among G20 countries and developing- country partners.

Several other donors are discussing the CE as a potential new focus area for development assistance. Few detailed strategies have yet emerged, but early examples include Denmark’s strategic sector cooperation agreement with Indonesia on ‘circular economy and waste management’; a similar agreement with Kenya on

‘circular economy, cleaner manufacturing, regulation and enforcement’; and the Norwegian international development minister’s highlighting in April 2018 of the CE as a priority in Norway’s international development policy, with a focus on cooperation with developing countries to establish profitable value chains for waste.

Commitments to supporting CE initiatives in the developing world have also emerged in other countries, in response to a surge in public awareness of the global waste challenge. The Memorandum of Understanding on Circular Economy Cooperation between the EU and China, signed in July 2018, could provide a vehicle through which to broaden CE cooperation and leadership. Under the MoU, the EU and China agree to cooperate on ‘dialogue on the design, planning and implementation of strategies, legislation, policies, and research’, ‘strategic exchanges on management systems and policy tools such as eco-design, eco- labelling, extended producer responsibility and green supply chains’, ‘strategic exchanges on best practices of circular economy’, and ‘exchanges on investments in and financing of circular economy’. Such modes of cooperation could, in theory, be extended to third countries, including in sub-Saharan Africa where both the EU and China have significant investment interests and existing donor programs.

Cooperation between donors and multilateral agencies can provide a further avenue through which to advance CE activities and strategies. The UK’s Department for International Development, for example, has partnered with the UN Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) to develop the Sustainable Manufacturing and Environmental Pollution programme.

For international financial institutions seeking to support the implementation of the SDGs and the Paris Agreement, investments in CE innovations or value chains could be used to reinforce and accelerate existing programmes of sustainable development. Many multilateral development banks are scaling up their activities in the CE space and are also setting aside specific funding pots for CE approaches. Some examples of MDB activity include the following: European Investment Bank (EIB); European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD); World Bank: The bank’s technical assistance programme ‘China: Promoting a Circular Economy’ supported the development of national legislation on the CE in China in 2009; African Development Bank (AfDB).

Among the countries that have formulated their circular economy national policies and strategies, the EU and China are the most typical examples of comprehensive circular economy packages. Being the frontrunners in the transition towards circular economy, the EU’s and China’s experiences in both policy making and actual implementation could become a benchmark for other countries. Besides, from a trade perspective, the intra-EU trade in circular goods and services itself could be valuable lessons for Vietnam in formulating its trade policies. Therefore, in the following sections, the research will focus on circular economy practices in China and the EU.

Circular economy practices in China

China’s rapid economic growth demands major supplies of all basic industrial commodities. The country’s rapid industrialization in the last decades has engendered serious problems of depletion of natural resources, degradation of major ecosystems, and pollution extending far beyond its borders. China, then, puts efforts to harmonise economic development and environmental protection. For more than 15 years, China’s government has been a frontrunner on circular economy policies, with a focus on addressing pollution, promoting resource efficiency, and industrial ecology. If China can achieve its goal of increasing efficiency of resource utilization, this will have global impact. For Vietnam, China is the country’s neighbor and also among the biggest trading partners. The two countries share many similarities in terms of economy, culture, society, politics, etc. Given the above analysis, it will be useful for Vietnam to study the example of China’s circular economy practices.

The Circular Economy Promotion Law of the People’s Republic of China, which was adopted at the 4th session of the Standing Committee of the 11th National People’s Congress of the People’s Republic of China on August 29, 2008, came into force on January 1, 2009. The Law has 7 chapters including: Chapter I – General

Principles, Chapter II – Basic Management Rules, Chapter III – Reduction, Chapter IV – Reusing and Recycling, Chapter V – Incentive Measures, Chapter VI – Legal Liabilities and Chapter VII – Supplementary Provisions. It focuses on development plans, extended producer responsibilities, supervision management systems for key enterprises with high energy and water consumptions, circular economy indices, statistics, and other management systems. In the Law, the requirements for circular economy development are proposed, covering production techniques, equipment, resource exploitation, recycling of waste materials, comprehensive resource utilisation, reduction, and other aspects. As proposed in Chapter V - Incentive Measures of the law, the government shall encourage circular economy through special funds, technical support, tax incentives, investment, finance, price, government procurement, and other aspects.

While laws and regulations are legal protection and play supporting role in the development of circular economy, comprehensive policies play the general guiding role and include action plans, programmes, and opinions. Developing circular economy, China adopts both environmental, industrial and economic policies⁴⁶. One example of environmental policy is that China's Environmental Protection Ministry develops pollutant emission standards for different industries so that enterprises must develop strategies for low material consumption and low emissions. Economic policies could include tax, fiscal, monetary and price policies to develop circular economy⁴⁷. Preferential tax and financial incentives are also adopted to stimulate the development of cleaner production in enterprises. Preferential tax rating is implemented in enterprises dedicated to waste material recycling and comprehensive resource utilisation. Price measures are adopted to regulate industries with high-energy consumption for utilisation of resources and energy.

In a research by Ogunmakinde (2019), his finding is that China's circular economy practices are primarily implemented at the design, production, consumption and waste management stages and at the enterprise, regional, and social levels. As illustrated in Figure 2.2. below, eco design and environmentally friendly designs are introduced at the design stage to protect the quality of the environment. Cleaner production, eco industrial park, and low-carbon cities are implemented to improve the circularity of products at the manufacturing/production stage. For consumers play a vital role in ensuring that materials are continually circulated at the end of their useful lives, minimizing pollution, Chinese consumers are encouraged to live a low-carbon lifestyle through green purchase, sharing, and renting services. With regards to waste management, China adopts reuse, recycling, waste trade markets, and industrial urban symbiosis to allow waste products to remain in circulation.

Circular economy practices in the EU

The EU is another important trade partner of Vietnam (Details of the EU – Vietnam trade relation to be presented the next session). With a Circular Action Plan in place since 2015 and many other relevant regulatory & policy documents, the EU's practice of Circular Economy implementation is a good reference for other countries to look at circular economy from the perspective of a developed block.

Circular economy policy

Promoting the transition towards a circular economy and protecting the environment and human health in Europe have emerged as pillars of the EU policy for sustainable development⁴⁹. Europe has adopted a comprehensive circular economy package for that purpose in 2015 and becomes a frontrunner with its circular economy approach. The CE package is expected to help European businesses and consumers to make the transition to a stronger and more circular economy where resources are used in a more sustainable way. The package included 04 legislative proposals on waste, revising the following legal acts:

The Circular Economy Package also introduced a Circular Economy Action Plan⁵⁰, a set of 54 actions to “close the loop” and support the achievement of the UN Sustainable Development Goals, in particular SDG12 on sustainable production and consumption. The list of actions is divided according to each stage of products' life cycle – production, consumption, waste management, market for secondary raw materials – and to five priority

areas – plastics, food waste, critical raw materials, construction and demolition, biomass and bio-based products. Other measures relate to innovation, investment and monitoring processes (See details of the actions in Annex 04).

Among the actions delivered through the action plan, it is worth noting the introduction of a EU Strategy on Plastics⁵¹ as well as a Directive on Single-Use plastics, a Communication on the interface between waste, chemicals and product legislation, a new Regulation on fertilising products⁵⁴ – introducing harmonised requirements for organic fertilisers manufactured from SRMs - and a Monitoring Framework for the Circular Economy.

In 2019, the European Commission published a report on the implementation of the action plan, stating that all 54 actions had been put in place at the EU level. Actions to support the transition to a circular economy have been gaining increasing political support also at the Member State level. Several member States have introduced National Circular Economy Action Plans or Roadmaps.

With regards to the latest developments in the implementation of the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, in January 2018 the European Commission adopted a Europe-wide EU Strategy for Plastics in the Circular Economy. Accordingly, by 2030, all plastic packaging should be reusable or recyclable in a cost-effective manner. Signed by over 250 businesses, governments and other organizations, it commits signatories to eliminate unnecessary plastic items; innovate to ensure plastics can be composted, recycled or reused; and circulate plastic items to prevent their damaging the environment. The EU's latest circular economy movement is the Commission's adoption of the New Circular Economy Action Plan – one of the building block of the EU Green Deal – on March 11, 2020.

The EU's trade policies in relation to circular economy

In today's globalised world, raw materials, technologies, products, components, waste, and services are produced, traded and consumed cross-border. The circular economy transition of the EU therefore has the potential impact beyond its geographical border.

The EU's trade in recyclables

The EU is the world's largest exporter and a major importer of non-hazardous waste destined for recovery (recycling). The value of the recyclable raw materials imported from non-EU countries stood at €9.2 billion in 2018. On the other hand, exports of recyclable raw materials from the EU to non-EU countries were worth €14.0 billion in 2018. Turkey and China were the main destinations for the EU's exports of recyclable raw materials. The largest tonnage of recyclable raw materials were imported from China, Norway, and the United States, Russia in 2018.

When considering prices and quantities traded in the three major secondary materials markets in the European Union alone, volumes are already very substantial. Between 2002 and 2012, the combined markets for waste glass (€2.6bn), paper (€56.2bn) and plastics (€26.4bn) in the EU alone amounted to €85.2 billion in current prices, with much potential still untapped. Electronic goods also have a large untapped circularity potential. A study from the United Nations University and UNCTAD assessed a potential of €48 billion of savings in metals and plastics present in e-waste alone.

Plastic and plastic waste are traded worldwide and a significant proportion of plastic waste is traded, both inside the EU and between the EU and other parts of the world. Exporting plastic waste from the EU to Asia is a means of dealing with insufficient recycling capacities in the EU, plus profit can be made from export activities. EU exports of plastic waste to countries outside the EU amounted to around 150 000 tonnes per month at the start of 2019.⁵⁸ Many of the countries to which the EU exports its plastic waste are still in their infancies with respect to developing waste management. For example, plastic products manufacturing and reprocessing plants in China have no standard operating procedures, no quality standards and no inspections to investments in large

manufacturing plants. Imported waste is often not processed in accordance with European standards and might even be dumped or burned in unregulated ways.⁵⁹

Recent restrictions on imports of plastic waste in China, combined with some types of plastic being added to the United Nations Basel Convention, the export of plastic waste to other countries is becoming more difficult. The EU must find circular and climate-friendly ways of managing its plastic waste e.g. by increasing reuse and recycling. The same applies for other wastes in order to reach a comprehensive circular economy.

3. Conclusion

Bilateral trade and investment links between the EU and Vietnam have steadily strengthened since the two sides established formal diplomatic relations in 1996. For years, the EU has been the second largest overseas market for Vietnamese products and Vietnam's fourth most important two-way trading partner after China, South Korea and the US. This has been a dominant trend since 2004, when the EU and Vietnam concluded the bilateral negotiations of Vietnam's accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO). 2017 witnessed a historical milestone in bilateral trade when Vietnam became one of the ten largest exporters to the EU for the first time.

The main EU imports from Vietnam include telecommunications equipment, clothing and food products. The EU mainly exports goods such as machinery and transport equipment, chemicals and agricultural products to Vietnam. The EU also reaches out to Vietnam with services such as banking, maritime transport and postal.

The EU-Vietnam Free Trade Agreement (EVFTA) is considered the "most modern and ambitious agreement ever concluded between the EU and a developing country". The agreement is an instrument to protect the environment and to sustain social progress in Vietnam. It commits Vietnam to apply the Paris Agreement. Parliament has just approved the EU-Vietnam free trade and investment protection deals in February, 2020. Once the Council formally concludes the trade agreement and the parties notify each other that their procedures are closed, it can enter into force and bring mutual benefits to both Parties.

The EU's transition towards circular economy and implications for Vietnam

The EVFTA does mentions "sustainable production and/or consumption" in its Trade & Sustainable development Chapter: "Parties may work together in [...] sharing information and experience about trade-related aspects concerning the definition and implementation of green growth strategies and policies, including but not limited to sustainable production and consumption, climate change mitigation and adaptation, and environmentally sound technology", but only limited to the call for parties to facilitate trade in relevant products and cooperation for good practices without bringing parties to commitments to favor each other....

Many policies implemented to drive the transition to a circular economy are adopted domestically, either at the EU or Member State level, including EPR schemes and standards for products to promote their durability, reusability and recyclability in an efficient – and safe – manner. While these policies deliver circularity benefits in the geographic context they are adopted, those benefits are likely to be significantly reduced once products or waste material are imported and/or exported, creating barriers to effective recycling of waste or uptake of secondary raw materials.

Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes aimed at ensuring that producers and manufacturers take responsibility for the end-of-life of their products and the associated packaging, with possible global consequences. If EPR raises the costs for EU firms relative to non-EU firms, this might result in EU's circular economy measures providing an unintended and counterproductive advantage to third-country producers with a lower level of circular responsibility.

REFERENCES

- i. UNEP (2015), *Global Waste Management Outlook*.

- ii. *OCED (2017), Trade and environment interactions: Governance Issues.*
- iii. *Moving towards a circular economy for plastics in the EU by 2030, THINK 2030, 2018, Institute for European Environmental Policy (IEEP).*
- iv. *European Commission (2019), Report from the commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the regions on the implementation of the Circular Economy Action Plan.*
- v. *Institute for European Environmental Policy (2019), EU circular economy and trade: Improving policy coherence for sustainable development.*
- vi. *Nguyen Trinh Thanh Nguyen (2018), Europeanization in Aid for trade – The case study of EU aid for trade to Vietnam.*
- vii. *European Commission (2020), Commission Staff Working Document: Leading the way to a global circular economy: state of play and outlook.*
- viii. *UNCTAD (2018), Trade Policy Frameworks for Developing Countries: A Manual of Best Practices.*
- ix. *European Commission (2020), Commission Staff Working Document: Evaluation of Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 June 2006 on shipments of waste.*
- x. *European Commission (2018), COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy.*
- xi. *Prabhakar, Sweta (2018), Managing the Transition through Multilevel Governance, in Anbumozhi, Venkatachalam and F. Kimura (eds.), Industry 4.0: Empowering ASEAN for the Circular Economy, Jakarta: ERIA, pp.325- 360.*
- xii. *Chatham House (2019), The US-China Trade Dispute: What impact on the circular economy?.*
- xiii. *Olabode Emmanuel Ogunmakinde (2019), A Review of Circular Economy Development Models in China, Germany and Japan, MDPI.*
- xiv. *Konrad von Moltke (1999), Trade and the environment - The linkages and the politics, Paper for the Roundtable on Canberra, 25 August 1999.*
- xv. *Environment, Trade and SARD: Concepts, Issues and Tools. Background Paper 4: Environment and Trade.*
- xvi. *Material Economics (2018): The Circular Economy: A powerful force for climate mitigation;*
- xvii. *Arno Behrens (2016): Time to connect dots: What is the link between climate change policy and the circular economy?, CEPS Policy Brief, Nr. 337.*
- xviii. *IPPC (2019), Global Warming of 1.5oC.*
- xix. *Doug Woodring (2019), Basel Convention Amendments on Plastics Could Hinder Efforts to Reduce Pollution.*
- xx. *Circle Economy (2019), the Circularity Gap Report*
- xxi. *Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2019), Completing the picture how the circular economy tackles climate change.*
- xxii. *Zhe Liu, Michelle Adams, Tony R. Walker (2018), Are exports of recyclables from developed to developing countries waste pollution transfer or part of the global circular economy?*
- xxiii. *Patrick Schroeder, Paul Dewick, Simonove Kusi-Sarpong, Joerge S. Hofstetter (2018), Circular Economy and power relations in global value chains: Tensions and trade-offs for lower income countries.*
- xxiv. *OECD (2018) International Trade and the Transition to a More Resource Efficient and Circular Economy: A Concept Paper.*
- xxv. *Laura Wellesley, Felix Preston, Joahanna Lehne (2019), An Inclusive Circular Economy: Priorities for Developing Countries.*
- xxvi. *UNCTAD (2018), Circular Economy: The New Normal?, Policy Brief No. 61, May 2018, Geneva: UNCTAD*

- xxvii. Yamaguchi, S. (2018), *International Trade and the Transition to a More Resource Efficient and Circular Economy–Concept Paper*, Paris: OECD
- xxviii. McCarthy, Dellink and Bibas (2018), *The Macroeconomics of the Circular Economy Transition: A Critical Review of Modelling Approaches*.
- xxix. European Commission (2020), *COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT: Leading the way to a global circular economy: state of play and outlook*
- xxx. Schroder P., (2019), *The US-China Trade Dispute: What impact on the circular economy?*
- xxxi. Li, W. and W. Lin (2016), 'Circular Economy Policies in China', in Anbumozhi, V. and J. Kim (eds.), *Towards a Circular Economy: Corporate Management and Policy Pathways. ERIA Research Project Report 2014-44*, Jakarta: ERIA, pp.95-111.
- xxxii. European Commission (2015), *COM(2015) 614 final. Closing the loop – An EU action plan for the Circular Economy*.
- xxxiii. European Commission (2018), *COM(2018)28 final. A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy*.
- xxxiv. European Commission (2019), *DIRECTIVE(EU) 2019/904 on the reduction of certain plastic products on the environment*.
- xxxv. European Commission (2018), *COM (2018) 32 final. Communication on the interface between waste, chemicals and product legislation*
- xxxvi. European Commission (2019) *Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilizing products*.
- xxxvii. Eurostat (2018) *Monitoring Framework for the circular economy*
- xxxviii. Eurostat (2019), *trade in recyclable raw materials*.
- xxxix. European Environment Agency (2019), *the plastic waste trade in the circular economy. Published on 28 Oct, 2019*.
- xl. Dröge, Susanne; Schenuit, Felix (2018): *Mobilising EU trade policy for raising environmental standards: the example of climate action; IEEP Working Paper; Brussels 2018*
- xli. Valles G. (2016), *The circular economy in international trade. Published on 05 December 2016 on UNTAD.org*
- xlii. European Commission (2019), *Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, The European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the implementation of the Circular Economy Action Plan*.
- xliii. Dinh, Thao Hoa and H. L. Nguyen (2018), 'An Assessment of Vietnamese Firms' Readiness to Adopt a Circular Economy', in Anbumozhi, Venkatachalam and F. Kimura (eds.), *Industry 4.0: Empowering ASEAN for the Circular Economy*, Jakarta: ERIA, pp.161-202.
- xliv. Huynh Trung Hai (2012), *International trade in recyclable materials: Lost or Opportunity*
- xlv. *Opening remarks at a workshop on the circular economy and climate change organized by the governments of Costa Rica and Finland on 25 November at the WTO, Deputy Director-General Alan Wolff*.
- xlvi. *The EU – Vietnam Free Trade Agreement (EVFTA)*
- xlvii. *Law on Foreign Trade Management No.05/2017/QH14 (2017)*
- xlviii. *Circular No. 09/2018/TT-BTNMT on promulgation of National Technical Regulations on Environment Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 of the European Parliament and of Council of 14 June 2006 on shipments of waste*.
- xlix. *Commission Regulation (EC) No 1418/2007 of 29 November 2007 concerning the export for recovery of certain waste listed in Annex III or IIIA to Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council to certain countries to which the OECD Decision on the control of transboundary movements of wastes does not apply*.
- l. *Decision of the Council C(2001)107/FINAL concerning the control of transboundary movements of wastes destined for recovery operations, as amended by C(2004)20*.